

Charge transfer complexes of metronidazole and tinidazole with quinones and their thermodynamics

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Interaction between two well-known amebicides, metronidazole and tinidazole with two well-known electron acceptors chloranil and para benzoquinone and the thermodynamics aspects of such complexes have been discussed. The drugs have been found to form reversible complexes with the said acceptors.

The 'drug action' is the consequence of a number of physico-chemical reactions in a biological system^{1,2}. Charge-transfer interactions is one of the important physico-chemical reactions occurring in biological systems. It is reasonable to believe that studies of charge-transfer interactions of drugs with other biological molecules may throw light on some aspects of drug receptor interactions, a complicated process involving a number of different physico-chemical reactions.

Quinones are important compounds intimately associated with electron transport and oxidative phosphorylation processes in biological systems³. Metronidazole and tinidazole are important pharmaceutical agents used widely for the treatment of amoebiasis and giardia lamblia⁴.

Naturally, charge transfer interactions of these drugs with quinones and the stability of the complexes if formed, may provide some useful information, a compilation of data of which are important in understanding the role of charge-transfer processes in complicated biological processes.

These considerations led us to study the thermodynamics of charge transfer complexes between metronidazole (MDZ) and tinidazole (TDZ) with para benzoquinone (PBQ) and chloranil (Cl-PBQ).

Results and discussion

Assuming the composition of the complex to be 1 : 1, the equilibrium constant of the complexes

can be written as

$$K = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \times \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} = \frac{x}{(C_1-x)(C_2-x)} \quad (2)$$

where C_1 , C_2 and x are the concentrations of D (MDZ or

TDZ) and A (PBQ or Cl-PBQ) and the complex respectively.

In diluted solutions of non-electrolytes in acetonitrile,

$\frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A}$ has been assumed to be unity.

Both PBQ and Cl-PBQ are known to show strong absorption in UV region. MDZ and TDZ also show absorption in the UV region. The addition of PBQ or Cl-PBQ to MDZ or TDZ are characterized by absorption changes and shift in the absorption maxima indicating complex formation. The salient features are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of λ_{\max} (nm) of charge-transfer complexes their components in acetonitrile solvent and the structure

Complexes/ components	λ_{\max} (nm)
MDZ	320, 230
TDZ	320, 230
PBQ	290
Cl-PBQ	285
PBQ + MDZ	320, 293-294
PBQ + TDZ	321, 293-294
Cl-PBQ + MDZ	320, 290
Cl-PBQ + TDZ	320, 290

In general Benesi-Hildebrand⁵ or Scott equation⁶ is utilised to calculate K where usually donor is taken in large excess and only the complex absorb in the region of measurement. However, the reliability of most of the association constants determined using D in excess compared to A is doubtful. From a critical assessment of data Foster⁷ suggested the acceptable association constant values can be obtained either from NMR shift or from optical measurements where $[D] \approx [A]$. This led us to use concentrations

[D] ≈ [A] in our measurements.

Led d and d_1 be the optical densities of the complex and donor respectively, we have

$$d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l \quad (3)$$

$$d = \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x)l + \epsilon \times l \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } x = \frac{d - d_1}{\epsilon - \epsilon_1} \text{ since } l = 1 \text{ cm} \quad (5)$$

Putting the value of x in (1) and rearranging, the expression (6) can be obtained⁸⁻¹⁰.

$$\frac{C_1}{d - d_1} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x)K} \quad (6)$$

Initially, x was taken to be zero and from the plot of

$$\frac{C_1}{d - d_1} \text{ against } \frac{1}{C_2}, \frac{1}{\epsilon - \epsilon_1} \text{ was obtained.}$$

This was utilised to get refined value of x .

The iteration was continued until the constancy in K and $\frac{1}{\epsilon - \epsilon_1}$ values were obtained. Usually three iterations are sufficient to get accurate K -values. In this way K -values at different temperatures are obtained. Estimates of ΔH° for the complex formation have been determined from the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$, assuming ΔH° to remain constant in the temperature range studied (293 to 313 K). The values of ΔS° have been obtained from the relation.

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where, } \Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log K \quad (8)$$

The values of K , ΔG_{298}° , ΔH° and ΔS° values have been recorded in Table 2.

The results given in Table 1 show that both MDZ and TDZ form fairly stable complexes with para benzoquinone and chloranil.

The MDZ complexes have been found to be slightly more stable. The replacement of $-\text{OH}$ by $-\text{SO}_2\text{Et}$ may lead to strain due to packaging imbalance or due to changed charge distribution making TDZ complexes less stable. Chloranil, due

Table 2. Values of K_{AD} , ϵ_{AD} , ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° of different charge-transfer complexes in acetonitrile

Complex	Temp. K	K_{AD}	$\epsilon_{AD} \times 10^4$	ΔG°	ΔH°	ΔS°
			$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	J K^{-1}
MDZ + Cl-PBQ	293	708.0				
	298	588.8				
	303	467.7	1.807	-15.83	-34.65	-63.2
	308	371.5				
	313	295.1				
TDZ + Cl-PBQ	293	631.0				
	298	501.2				
	303	416.9	1.717	-15.40	-31.89	-55.3
	308	331.1				
	313	275.4				
MDZ + PBQ	293	512.9				
	298	416.9				
	303	346.7	2.057	-14.97	-29.89	-50.1
	308	281.8				
	313	234.4				
TDZ + PBQ	293	501.2				
	298	407.4				
	303	331.1	1.967	-14.91	-29.13	-47.7
	308	281.8				
	313	218.8				

to its better electron accepting capability over para benzoquinone forms more stable complex than benzoquinone. The exact sites of action is different but in all probability interactions can be regarded as charge transfer complexes with structures I and II of which I appears to be more probable.

The results suggest the formation of reversible loose complex between quinone and the drugs.

These drugs are well absorbed by proteins and studies with calf-thymus DNA, indicate that metronidazole causes a loss of helical structure of DNA strand breakage and loss of function as template⁴. Naturally, MDZ or TDZ receptor interaction is associated with loose interaction like charge-transfer interaction, hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions.

The complex formation is accompanied by exothermic enthalpy changes and the enthalpy changes are of the order of -34 kJ mol^{-1} to -29 kJ mol^{-1} . The bands around 280–290 nm of the quinones are due to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and the shift occurs in this region when MDZ or TDZ is added to the quinones. The enthalpy changes for MDZ complexes are more exothermic compared to TDZ complexes. The values show that the complexes are fairly stable and the values are in agreement generally obtained in case of CT complexes though ΔH° values of CT complexes are few. However, complex formation is accompanied by negative entropy changes ($-63 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$ to $-47 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$). The enthalpy and entropy values are comparable to these typical charge-transfer complexes of chloranil and hydrocarbons¹¹. The decrease in entropy may suggest the decrease in the number of molecules and ordering of solvent environment and enthalpy change suggests relatively stable bond formation i.e. there is good overlapping of the molecules and the contribution of the excited state structure is appreciable. In absence of data in the gaseous state, the real picture of solvent effect on the thermodynamics of complexes are different. However, studies on charge transfer complexes involving drug molecules are important both from physico-chemical points of view and understanding of drug action.

Experimental

Metronidazole and tinidazole (reference standard) were obtained as gift. The drugs were crystallised from 50% aqueous alcohol, dried and used. The purity of the drugs were tested from melting point determination. Both MDZ and TDZ were obtained as off white crystals. The drugs were fairly soluble in water. Para benzoquinone (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by crystallisation. Chloranil (G.R., E. Merck) was crystallised twice from thiophene-free benzene (G.R., E. Merck) and then from acetone (G.R., E. Merck) and dried. The purity of the compounds were checked from melting point determination. Acetonitrile (G.R., E. Merck) was treated with K_2CO_3 and kept overnight. The decanted solution was further treated with P_2O_5 for an hour and distilled. Middle fraction was used immediately after distillation. Since the components and the complex absorb in the UV region, the wavelength for measure-

ment was selected to be 335 nm, where at the experimental concentration of 10^{-4} order there was no absorption for PBQ or Cl-PBQ. The complex formation was found to be instantaneous [evident from the shift in the absorbance maxima of drugs and changes in absorbances (Figs. 1, 2)] and the complexes are stable for several days. The association constants of the complexes were determined from the absorption measurements of drugs and the solutions obtained by mixing the acceptors and donors usually in different proportions at the desired wavelength.

Fig. 1. Variation of absorbance with wavelength (nm) in acetonitrile for (a) 0.8×10^{-3} PBQ, (b) 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ, (c) 0.8×10^{-3} (M) PBQ + 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ.

Fig. 2. Variation of absorbance with wavelength (nm) in acetonitrile for (a) 0.25×10^{-4} (M) Cl-PBQ, (b) 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ, (c) 0.23×10^{-4} (M) Cl-PBQ + 0.4×10^{-4} (M) MDZ.

For the determination of the enthalpy of reaction, the association constants were determined at several temperatures in the way described before. However for the preparation of solutions, the reactants were kept in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature for an hour before mixing. The mixtures and the suitable blanks were kept at

the desired temperature for two hours to enable the mixtures to attain equilibrium at the desired temperature.

The absorption measurements of the mixture and the blank solutions were taken at 335 nm as quickly as possible to avoid temperature fluctuations as far as practicable.

The absorbance measurements were made using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer controlled at 298 K.

Concentration range :

PBQ and Cl-PBQ : $0.2-0.4 \times 10^{-4} M$

MDZ and TDZ : $0.4-1.6 \times 10^{-4} M$

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